

2020-2021

ANNUAL REPORT ✨

10 YEARS OF #ASTRO4DEV

OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

10
years

Acknowledgements: The content in this booklet is based on OAD project reports, quarterly reports, press releases, and published articles. All images are courtesy of the projects.

ESO/C. Malin (p.8), NASA, ESA, and J. Nichols (p.14), ESO/S. Brunier (p.17), NASA/JSC (p.37), ESO/P. Horálek (p.40)

Cover image: This image was taken by Petr Horálek some 100 kilometres south of the Chajnantor Plateau, which is home to the Atacama Large Millimetre/submillimetre Array (ALMA). Credit: ESO/P. Horálek

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01

10 YEARS OF OAD ✨

December 2021

In 2008, when George Miley asked me to participate in a brainstorm around an IAU strategy, I was deeply honoured. I never imagined that, 13 years later, we would be looking back at a decade of the Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD) – a structure that was set up to implement the very plan that was born out of that 2008 meeting. Since that meeting, there have been many celebrated occasions: in 2009 the IAU Strategic plan 2010-2020 was ratified by the General Assembly in Brazil; in 2010 South Africa won the bid to host the OAD, which would be key to implementing that plan; in 2011 the OAD was launched in Cape Town, South Africa; at the 2012 IAU General Assembly in China, the OAD made its first impressions on the IAU membership, establishing strongly the importance of astronomy for development (as compared to developing astronomy) and kicking off its first two regional offices. By the 2015 IAU General Assembly in the US, the OAD had established 9 regional offices and a resolution for its continuation was adopted. In 2016, the OAD achieved significant recognition through the award of the Edinburgh Medal and at the 2018 General Assembly, a new IAU strategic plan was adopted for the 2020–2030 decade, with the OAD featuring significantly with a clear mandate distinct from its sister offices.

When the global pandemic struck in 2020, the OAD had 11 regional offices in place, and was experienced and agile enough to quickly react to the situation with an extraordinary call for COVID-related projects. Now, in 2021, as the OAD celebrates its 10th anniversary as well as a very positive external review, we do so in a world very different from the one in 2008. It is a world that has changed and continues to change rapidly, as disease, climate and other challenges threaten life as we know it.

The OAD and its global network are well placed to act constructively in such a landscape – in fact it has always been built into our DNA that we should continue to find ways in which we can help make the world a better place, addressing the challenges we face as humanity. The foundations of the OAD have been built on humility, openness and inclusion – the projects supported by the OAD come from communities around the world who themselves identify needs and design activities to address them. We have recognised, however, the essential need for interdisciplinary conversations in order to maximise the potential impact that astronomy, in all its aspects, can have on furthering sustainable development. The three flagships identified from OAD activities over the years (in short, astronomy for economic development; astronomy for humanity; and astronomy skills for development) all require partners from fields outside of astronomy in order to realise global impact. They also require funding and we are fortunate to now have the IAU fundraiser to support such activities.

The OAD's location on the African continent was not entirely coincidental. In the original discussions, and during the initial years of the OAD, there was a specific intention to focus on Africa due to the levels of developmental need as well as the potential of astronomy to make a significant impact on the continent's trajectory. This potential has been recognised by a number of African leaders who have driven efforts to leverage the field of astronomy for Africa's growth and development. In 2024, the IAU General Assembly will take place in Africa for the first time, and the OAD will be intimately involved in making this a significant event both for the continent and for the OAD's work globally.

On the occasion of this 10th anniversary of the OAD, it is paramount to recognise all the individuals and organisations who make the OAD what it is. Without mentioning individual names, I would like to state, without reservation, that the OAD would not be what it is, nor achieved what it has without the ongoing support of the core OAD team in Cape Town; the remote teams of reviewers, fellows and volunteers around the world; the 11 regional offices and their respective teams; the many project leaders and communities supported through the call for proposals; and of course our dedicated Steering Committee and principal organisations, the International Astronomical Union (IAU), and the National Research Foundation (NRF) and the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI) of South Africa. It is this global team of stakeholders who have contributed to the ongoing endeavour of using astronomy to make the world a better place!

Kevin Govender

Director, IAU Office of Astronomy for Development

OAD EXTERNAL REVIEW

The OAD underwent its second external review in early 2021. The panel, consisting of Professors Ian Corbett, Daya Reddy and You-Hua Chu, evaluated the 6 years from April 2014 to March 2020. The outcome was very positive with a recommendation to renew the OAD hosting in South Africa until 2027. This recommendation was later endorsed at a high-level meeting between the IAU, NRF and DSI.

“Our interviews with major stakeholders and the written input we have received endorse our conclusion that the performance of the OAD has been outstanding by any standards, and exceptional given the small size of the core team, its global remit and its relatively modest resources.”

– from the OAD External Review report

02

RESPONDING TO COVID-19 ✨

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a major effect on the OAD community and activities. Most projects and activities of the OAD and its regional offices have been postponed and sometimes cancelled. The OAD has looked at ways in which the astronomy community can play a role in addressing this global crisis and help mitigate some of its effects:

IAU CALL TO ACTION

The IAU Offices of Astronomy for Education (OAE), Development (OAD), Outreach (OAO), and Young Astronomers (OYA) believe that the astronomy community, including but not limited to professional and amateur astronomers, outreach & education practitioners and researchers, enthusiasts, and students possess varied skillsets which would be of help to the current situation. The Offices issued a call to action inviting the community to contribute skills and resources to alleviate some of the effects of the pandemic. We received more than a hundred submissions with astronomy educational resources and activities that can be done at home.

astro4dev.org/resources/covid-19/call-to-action-for-the-astronomy-community-in-the-time-of-covid-19

ASTRONOMY AND COVID-19

In April 2020, an OAD Fellow, Dr Marie Korsaga, was appointed to look at COVID-19 initiatives around the world, in order to assess how the global astronomy community were contributing to the alleviation of the crisis. And importantly, to try to explore new ways in which the astronomy community can potentially contribute, in partnership with relevant experts. She assembled information on scientists' efforts against the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on development, especially by researchers in astronomy and similar fields normally working in areas not related to infectious diseases. Examples include the South Africa Radio Astronomy Observatory's management of the National Ventilator Project for the local design and manufacturing of ventilators in the country; development of the Ventilator Intervention Technology Accessible Locally (VITAL) by NASA to assist patients who require breathing

assistance; studies modeling the spread of the virus; and campaigns to 'scientifically and sensitively' communicate information to the public.

astro4dev.org/resources/covid-19

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON DEVELOPMENT

What does COVID-19 mean for development? To help our community better understand the nature of the challenges and appreciate how their skills matter for development, Dr Tawanda Chingozha, OAD Fellow on Development Economics, published a number of articles.

astro4dev.org/resources/covid-19

CALL FOR PROPOSALS FOR COVID-19

The link between studying the stars and fighting a deadly pandemic may not be obvious, but astronomy and related fields possess strengths that can be applied to solving everyday challenges and benefitting communities. Previous Astronomy for Development projects, including those supported by the OAD, proved that astronomy's strengths and unique characteristics could be valuable in combating some of the challenges posed and exacerbated by the pandemic.

The OAD, the African Astronomical Society and the African Planetarium Association collaborated to provide small grants to support communities worldwide, especially underprivileged and underserved groups who bear the brunt of socio-economic upheavals. An Extraordinary Call for Proposals was launched in May 2020 for projects or partnerships that in some way use astronomy, in any

of its aspects (including skills, methodologies, tools, infrastructure, inspiration or even just networks of astronomers/enthusiasts), to help mitigate some of the negative effects of the pandemic. A total of 43 projects were selected and collectively granted a sum of 804,443 ZAR (approximately €40 000).

The selected projects include initiatives that developed and distributed educational materials in Mongolia, Canada, Chile, Ethiopia, and other countries to reach populations with poor or no internet access. These projects embedded astronomy content in their materials to take advantage of the inspiring potential of astronomy and use the natural laboratory of the sky to motivate and educate children and parents alike. A number of projects used astronomy in remote teaching and learning programmes to continue engaging students during school closures. From Ghana and Pakistan to Russia and Brazil, these projects leveraged low-tech and low-bandwidth solutions such as WhatsApp and SMS to reach those in underserved areas. Other projects in Italy, Greece, Mexico, and Nigeria combined art and astronomy to help lift people's spirits during these stressful times. Finally, projects also applied certain skills found in the astronomy community, such as data analytics and programming, to develop solutions to some of the challenges created by COVID-19. Some of these projects are highlighted in the following pages.

astro4dev.org/results-of-extraordinary-call-for-covid-19-related-proposals

E-LEARNING SUPPORT PROJECTS

NIGERIA

The NASRDA Centre for Basic Space Sciences, the host of the IAU OAD West African Regional Office, launched a free online learning platform with astronomy and physics content for high school and university students. The content is based on the West African Examinations Council and the curriculum of the University of Nigeria. All courses can be accessed upon registration. astro4dev.org/e-learning-platform-is-now-live

INDIA/GLOBAL

To plug the teaching-learning gap during COVID-19, the 'Astronomy from Archival Data' project trained university students on data processing techniques and analysis using freely available astronomy data. Participants were introduced to virtual observatory tools and programming techniques, and supported to formulate and develop projects. The training included special sessions on report writing and publishing in scientific journals. The content of the training is available in 80 Youtube videos.

 youtube.com/playlist?list=PLGf1ijrdazzELSYHF7RzQzTNbgihyW8hw

HAITI

The 'Astronomy Lakay Vodcasting' project broadcast basic astronomy videos in Haitian Creole during the COVID-19 lockdown in Haiti. Videos were disseminated on social networks such as facebook, whatsapp, twitter, as well as the blog of the Société Haïtienne d'Astronomie, which coordinated the project.

astro4dev.org/astronomy-videos-in-haitian-creole

PERU

Pregúntale A Un Astrónomo (Ask An Astronomer), coordinated by SPACE-FCF-UNMSM in Peru discussed astronomy and space science topics in an open conversation and easy-to-understand language, rather than as a lesson or a lecture. The videos (in Spanish) attracted the attention of children and young people at a time when formal education was challenging in middle and lower income countries.

 youtube.com/playlist?list=PLrvnNGo8WtEjtsU5DYY41LpK67AeX5_X0

SOUTH AFRICA

During the COVID-19 lockdown in South Africa, various initiatives were launched by universities to support students. Tutors however were not always priority recipients for support. This project used the OAD grant to pay for data bundles and tutors time.

astro4dev.org/time-and-data-for-tutors

USA

The Christa McAuliffe Center for Integrated Science Learning in the US facilitated a 4-week virtual summer program during the pandemic. Twenty seven girls were guided through activities, attended talks by experts, and used remote telescopes. The program was offered free of cost and thus prevented an increase in the learning gap between students who could and could not access enriching, after-school and out-of-school activities.

astro4dev.org/diy-universe-virtual-summer-program

OFFLINE LEARNING SUPPORT PROJECTS

MONGOLIA

The project developed and distributed an astronomy-themed “scientific box” to school students and teachers in remote areas of Mongolia. The box, developed by university students and professional and amateur astronomers, included handouts, video talks, presentations and lessons, which served as STEM education tools. During the lockdown, students and their families utilised the materials, observed the night sky and shared their findings.

astro4dev.org/astronomy-themed-scientific-box-mongolia

NAVAJO NATION, USA

The Navajo Nation was particularly hard hit by the pandemic. Teaching students online has been complicated by the fact that many households do not have electricity and those that do often have no or poor connections to the internet. The Native American Astronomy Outreach Program by Lowell Observatory continued their Book Club during the pandemic. The team sent each of the students a copy of the book for their grade level. The Book Club provided an offline method to engage students and retain their interest in STEM as well as improve student literacy.

astro4dev.org/native-american-astronomy-outreach-book-club

CHILE

The “Inspiring STEM learning through astronomy” project developed materials to inspire, encourage and educate students in rural areas of Chile whose studies were interrupted due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Their “pandemic learning support” booklet contains four activities for children to discover and connect with astronomy in a didactic and entertaining way, covering content such as: the universe and our solar system, constellations, layers of the earth and the coronavirus. Although

the booklet was prepared so that each activity can be guided by a teacher, it also promotes self-taught STEM learning through astronomy. It focuses on developing scientific skills, favoring exploration and experimentation with elements of the environment, observation, measurement with non-standardized units and simple material handling. The booklet (in Spanish) can be downloaded from the website.

astro4dev.org/stem-learning-through-astronomy-during-a-pandemic

**We are not alone,
we all live under the same stars.**

PHYSICAL AND MENTAL HEALTH SUPPORT PROJECTS

NIGERIA

Supported by an OAD grant, Astronomers Without Borders Nigeria has been assisting children at Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) camps in the country. The project inspires and educates children at the camps using astronomy and has established a solar-powered learning hub at one of the camps. To mitigate the impact of COVID-19 in the camps, the team delivered a hand washing station and posters about the dangers of COVID-19 and precautionary measures to be followed. They also provided hand sanitizers, disinfectants, face masks, other general cleaning supplies and food supplies. The team partnered with the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons and the Skilled Women Initiative to train women in the IDP camp to produce hand sanitizers.

astro4dev.org/covid-19-support-for-internally-displaced-persons

GHANA

The Ghana Radio Astronomy Observatory staff assisted their surrounding community by providing masks, sanitisers, and sensitising them about COVID-19 and how to protect themselves. PRAGSAC collaborated with the Ghana Space Science and Technology Institute, the Assembly woman of Kutunse electoral area and the Director of the NCCE for GA West/Amasaman to distribute 6 handwashing stations, 1000 face masks, 2000 flyers, soaps and hand sanitisers.

astro4dev.org/astronomy-observatory-staff-assist-community

SOUTH AFRICA

A project supported by the OAD developed a tool to allow easy access to healthcare facility data for the general public, decision-makers, NGOs, and others during the COVID-19 pandemic. This data is important to identify gaps, risks, and excess resources that can be deployed elsewhere. The information is available in multiple languages through the Google Translate widget. The collection of mapping visualisations is freely accessible and source code for the data visualisation platform is under an open source license.

astro4dev.org/healthcare-facility-data-for-south-africa-in-response-to-covid-19

GLOBAL

"Under the Same Stars" project by Astronomers Without Borders developed and launched an online social media campaign to bring awareness that stargazing can uniquely aid in relieving some mental stress during a time of crisis. Their campaign effectively spread the specific messaging: recognizing that while the global population is experiencing the same strains, we can all come together virtually and feel like a cohesive community regardless of any border. It received an overall positive response with increased engagement and participation in the videos.

astro4dev.org/astronomy-to-relieve-mental-stress

The background of the image is a detailed view of the planet Jupiter, showing its characteristic bands of orange, red, and white, with swirling cloud patterns and a prominent white equatorial band. In the center, the number '03' is displayed in a large, bold, white font. Surrounding the number is a graphic consisting of multiple white rectangular lines radiating outwards from a central point, resembling a sunburst or a starburst effect.

03

PUBLICATIONS

COVID BUDGET PRESSURES THREATEN CURIOSITY DRIVEN SCIENCE

Dr. Vanessa McBride published an article in The Conversation on the importance of curiosity-driven sciences like astronomy. She writes: "The pandemic has underscored that the world requires agility for survival. That makes blue skies science – which encourages curiosity and nimble thinking – perhaps more important than ever. But this will require a long-term view from governments and funders, particularly by providing decades of funding and freedom to allow scientists to ask the "why?" questions."

theconversation.com/covid-19-budget-pressures-threaten-curiosity-driven-science-thats-a-bad-thing-156586

HUMAN-DRIVEN DEVELOPMENT THROUGH SHARED OWNERSHIP AND DECENTRALIZATION

OAD Director, Kevin Govender, and Dr. Carolina Odman at the Inter-University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy in South Africa, contributed to the Rethinking Human Development initiative by the International Science Council (ISC) and the United Nations Development Programme. In their contribution, they explore how science and technology can fundamentally change the context in which human development is defined.

council.science/current/blog/human-driven-development-through-shared-ownership-and-decentralization

AS THE WORLD CHANGES, SCIENCE DOES TOO – AND THAT’S A GOOD THING

Kevin Govender and Dr. Odman also co-authored an article for The Conversation on the changing nature of science.

theconversation.com/as-the-world-changes-science-does-too-and-thats-a-good-thing-152688

IMPACT OF ASTRONOMICAL FACILITIES ON LOCAL DEVELOPMENT – PERSPECTIVES FROM SUTHERLAND

In recent times, the role of astronomy in socio-economic development has been in the spotlight. To understand development from the perspective of the community, a team from the OAD visited Sutherland, South Africa, that hosts the Southern Africa Large Telescope. The team interviewed various stakeholders to qualitatively assess the impact of the telescope and the Sutherland Observatory on local socio-economic development.

astro4dev.org/impact-of-astronomical-facilities-on-local-development

THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: REVEALING THE RESILIENCE OF AFRICA AND ITS GREAT POTENTIAL

OAD fellows, Drs Marie Korsaga and Amidou Sorgho wrote a blog about an Africa Month webinar where researchers, experts and political leaders discussed topics related to Africa’s innovations in the global fight against the COVID-19 pandemic.

astro4dev.org/the-covid-19-pandemic-revealing-the-resilience-of-africa-and-its-great-potential

PROJECTS

ANNUAL CALL FOR PROPOSALS

During the first quarter of the 2020/21 financial year, the OAD issued its 9th annual call for proposals. By the Stage 1 deadline of 31st May 2020, we received a total of 110 proposals. These were sent to Regional Offices for feedback, then to the review panel, in order to select those that will go into Stage 2. 38 Stage 2 proposals were submitted to the reviewers for evaluation. The reviewer oversight panel met during October, finalised recommendations, iterated with the full review panel and submitted to the OAD Steering Committee, who approved the recommendations in early November. Grant agreements were sent out during December. Later on, small additional grants were issued to 7 of the funded projects in order to assist with the implementation of their projects affected by the pandemic. In January 2021, the OAD launched a webinar series to support project leaders, and has been holding individual video meetings with each project for monitoring, implementation and evaluation support.

21 projects were selected to receive funding in 2021. These projects, which are addressing global challenges using astronomy-related innovations, include: online astronomy programmes in Indonesia and India; development of astronomy video content in Urdu to be used in Pakistan; training programmes for displaced populations in refugee camps in Algeria, Spain, Italy and Uganda; motivating and improving the welfare of prisoners in Nigeria; teaching coding using astronomical topics in Portugal, Mozambique and East Timor; mentoring and inspiring girls in primary schools in rural Kenya; and astronomy projects to celebrate indigenous culture and help students identify with their ancestral roots in Chile, Brazil, Cape Verde, Mozambique, São Tomé and Príncipe, Angola, and Portugal.

Although the call was announced in the early days of the COVID-19 pandemic, the OAD received an enthusiastic response from the community with 110 applications submitted. In total, £109 944 was granted to the funded projects.

List of projects funded, in alphabetical order

- ◆ AMANAR 2.0: A refuge in the stars, **ALGERIA, SPAIN, ITALY**
- ◆ Asteroids workshop: A rocky adventure, **CHILE**
- ◆ Astro Sprint, **INDIA**
- ◆ Astrobus, **NIGERIA**
- ◆ Astrolab Distant Training, **SOUTHERN, EASTERN AND WEST AFRICAN COUNTRIES**
- ◆ Astronomy for Environmental Protection in Gobi desert, **MONGOLIA**
- ◆ Astronomy Motivation Activities in rural India, **INDIA**
- ◆ Astro-prison, **NIGERIA**
- ◆ Code learning with astronomical ideas, **PORTUGAL, MOZAMBIQUE, EAST TIMOR**
- ◆ COVID-19 in Amazonas – Astronomy strikes back!, **BRAZIL**
- ◆ Elimisha Msichana. Elimisha Jamii na Astronomia, (Swahili for “educate a girl, educate the entire community with astronomy”), **KENYA**
- ◆ Empowering Rational Capacity through Astronomy: A Distant Learning Approach from Bosscha Observatory, **INDONESIA**
- ◆ Empowerment of Disadvantaged Rural Girl Children as Social Change Agents through Basic Education in Astronomy, **INDIA**
- ◆ Interdisciplinary Radio Astronomy, **GLOBAL**
- ◆ Knowledge access and sharing through Cultural Astronomy in Uganda’s Refugee settlements and Host Communities, **UGANDA**

- ◆ Open Astronomy Clubs for Quality Education, Gender Equality and Distribution of Telescopes, **CAMEROON**
- ◆ OruMbya — Astronomy as fuel of life: the resilience of stars in Yoruba, Afro-Brazilian and Indigenous Cosmogony, **BRAZIL, CAPE VERDE, MOZAMBIQUE, SÃO TOMÉ AND PRINCIPE, ANGOLA AND PORTUGAL**
- ◆ Pan-African School for Emerging Astronomers 2021, **AFRICA**
- ◆ Rediscovering Identity through Astronomy, **CHILE**
- ◆ Upliftment of Space Technology and Astronomy Cell in Himalayas, **INDIA**
- ◆ Video Astronomy Lessons for Pakistani School Children, **PAKISTAN**

The OAD has also compiled a list of recommended proposals that were approved by the reviewers but could not be funded. One can browse through the Recommended list on the website and contact us for more details or to support one or more projects.

NEW REVIEWERS

The OAD's review panel is responsible for evaluating and selecting projects from the proposals submitted in the annual call. In early 2021, the OAD called for new reviewers and following an overwhelming response, selections were made on the basis of skills, experience, geographic locations, gender and cultural diversity. The review panel now has 50 members representing 28 countries.

astro4dev.org/review-panel

UPDATES FROM SELECTED PROJECTS

PAN-AFRICAN SCHOOL FOR EMERGING ASTRONOMERS

The Pan-African School for Emerging Astronomers (PASEA), an innovative short course for African university students, published an article in Nature Astronomy on its unique features, impact, and the future. PASEA aims to build a critical mass of astronomers in Africa and exchange ideas about teaching across continents. The program has been postponed to 2022 due to COVID-19 induced delays. PASEA was previously the West African International Summer School for Young Astronomers which was funded twice by the OAD.

astro4dev.org/pan-african-school-for-emerging-astronomers

“The astronomy classes have helped develop the learners’ interest in science. The classes have also improved the children’s emotional development in terms of independence and self esteem.”

– Feedback from a teacher at the Molo Mhlaba school, South Africa

VIRTUAL, GLOBAL MENTORSHIP PROGRAM FOR WOMEN AND GIRLS

Like other STEM fields, astronomy suffers from under-representation of women and minorities and lack of role models to inspire the next generation of scientists. The She Speaks Science project aims to make science accessible and promote women in STEM through stories of inspiring women in STEM from all around the globe.

In 2021, the project launched PENTA, a 5-month mentorship program, designed as a 5-by-5 matrix, with women selected across 5 regions (Africa, Latin & North America, Middle East, Europe, Asia) at 5 different career stages (executive, professional, university student, high schooler, schooler). Within this matrix of 25 women and girls, each member mentors and gets mentored in an interactive and one-to-one environment (for example, a university student is mentored by a professional and mentors a high school student).

astro4dev.org/category/scheherazade-speaks-science

AFTER-SCHOOL ASTRONOMY PROGRAM ADAPTS FOR COVID-19

The Astro Molo Mhlaba project targets the issues of inclusivity in science in South Africa by engaging its most underrepresented group – black girls from underserved communities – in astronomy programmes at various stages of education. Through its regular programs such as Astro clubs and Astro academy and long-term structural support, it motivates girls to pursue a career in STEM, and provides them with the tools required to turn their ambitions into reality.

Due to COVID-19 lockdowns, many school children lost substantial learning time in school and after-school activities. Since the target beneficiaries lacked access to online learning, the project printed and distributed materials to the students -astronomy inspired calendars featuring women who have achieved amazing feats in STEAM, introduction to astronomy workbooks, and primary science workbooks that incorporated astronomy, chemistry, natural science and life sciences. A few, socially-distanced, in-person classes took place during the weeks when schools were open.

KATHMANDU ASTROPHYSICS SCHOOL 2020

The third Kathmandu Astrophysics School on "Introduction to astronomical techniques and data analysis" was held in two phases. The first component was an online program covering introductory level astrophysical coding in Python, key concepts and techniques used in observational astrophysics, professional development and teaching skills. The second component was a two-week, full-time in-person program held in Pokhara, Nepal. KAS aims to mentor and upskill students of astrophysics in both professional and academic areas through engagement with a highly qualified international faculty.

astro4dev.org/applications-open-for-3rd-kathmandu-astrophysics-school

ASTRONOMY TO SUPPORT AN INDIGENOUS VILLAGE IN BRAZIL

Under Other Skies, an OAD funded project, aims to collect native narratives, chants, and sky myths of the indigenous Maxakali people in Brazil. The project is being conducted in Aldeia Nova in Minas Gerais, and involves indigenous researchers, shamans, and elders of the village collaborating with anthropologists and educators of the Federal University of Minas Gerais, and astronomers and educators of the University of São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro. To overcome the challenges of COVID-19 and to support the community during this time, the project team have installed an internet connection in the village, and are supporting independent recording and production of material on indigenous astronomy as well as launching a virtual gallery for sharing Maxakali astronomical knowledge and their perspective of the world.

astro4dev.org/astronomy-support-indigenous-village

ASTRONOMY LEARNING HUB INSTALLED AT IDP CAMP IN NIGERIA

The IDP CAO (Internally Displaced People- Children's Astronomy Outreach) project was awarded a second grant in 2020. Project activities, postponed due to the pandemic, were launched in March 2021 at the new Kuchingoro IDP camp. A team of scientists and counsellors, from the Nigerian National Space Research and Development Agency, Astronomers Without Borders-Nigeria, and the Nigerian Commission for Refugees, Migrants and IDP's, used astronomy and counselling to counsel, heal and inspire children in the camps. They installed a solar-powered learning hub at the camp.

awbnigeria.org/idp-children-astronomy-outreach-project

“I was the first person to receive a PhD in astrophysics from a Lebanese university. Through She Speaks Science, I’ll make sure I’m not the last.”

– Dr Ghina M. Halabi, coordinator of She Speaks Science OAD project and mentor in the Space4Women Network by the UN Office for Outer Space Affairs

FLAGSHIPS

ASTRONOMY FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

This Flagship aims to use an astronomical facility, such as an observatory or planetarium, as a "hub" to stimulate various socio-economic benefits for the local community. Benefits could include job creation through astronomy-related tourism; community skills development; educational programmes; stimulation of local innovation; alternative activities for youth in order to keep away from negative/harmful activities; and infrastructure development.

OAD Fellow Amidou Sorgho gathered background information, lessons from past projects, and documented guidelines for anyone planning to run interventions under this Flagship.

astro4dev.org/sustainable-local-socio-economic-development-through-astronomy-guidelines

SHORT FILM: "THE DAILY LIFE OF A YOUNG WOMAN IN A REMOTE VILLAGE"

Stanzin Dolkar is a young woman who resides in Maan, a remote village in the Indian Himalayas. In 2019, she was trained to be an astroguide by the Global Himalayan Expedition (GHE) for the Astrostays project. This short film by Boris Wilmar, Baka films, follows the daily routine of Dolkar and the impact of astronomy on her life.

▶ youtube.com/watch?v=OglBH61uKvo&ab_channel=BakaFilms

ASTROSTAYS: COMMUNITY-DRIVEN ASTROTOURISM FOR CREATING SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS

Astrostays is a community-driven astrotourism model that puts communities at its heart. The program is aimed at empowering and strengthening communities by diversifying economic bases and creating new opportunities for livelihood creation using astrotourism. This model is an innovative form of experiential and

sustainable tourism that generates economic benefits for remote and rural regions of the world that have access to clear night skies while creating unique life-changing experiences for travelers.

Sonal Asgotraa, the project manager of Astrostays, was invited to present at the 2020 International Dark-Sky Association Conference. Her 15 minute presentation provides an overview of the concept and its impact on the community so far.

astro4dev.org/astrostays-community-driven-astrotourism-for-creating-sustainable-livelihoods-presentation-at-ida-conference-2020

The OAD and GHE participated in a special webinar on "Astro- Tourism: The Next Frontier of Nature-based Tourism" hosted by the Ministry of Tourism in India.

CALL FOR COLLABORATION ON ASTROSTAYS

As the tourism sector recovers from the global pandemic, astrotourism offers new opportunities for the industry and local communities. Astrotourism is uniquely placed to grow in our socially distanced world. Star-gazing, as an experiential form of tourism, encourages one to slow down and introspect. It has the power to inspire, entertain, evoke curiosity, and encourage a positive state of mind. The rural, outdoor location is an added benefit. The OAD aims to work with the astronomy community, including research institutions, amateur and professional astronomers, communicators, outreach professionals, as well as tourism players to establish astrotourism projects to benefit communities around the world.

Astrostays, combining astronomy and homestays, is our most successful project under this Flagship. The OAD envisages other models which similarly pair suitable tourism products and contexts with astronomy to benefit communities. Individuals and organizations interested in collaborating with the IAU OAD are requested to email info@astro4dev.org.

astro4dev.org/flagship-1-astrostays/

ASTROPARK

An astronomical park or AstroPark in a rural area, not far from existing tourist attractions, will help to stimulate tourism and economic development around the park, spark an interest in STEM and learning through the awe of astronomy, and bring awareness about ecosystem preservation. The OAD is working with the GHE to establish an AstroPark in partnership with the Madhya Pradesh Tourism Board of India.

ASTRONOMY FOR PEACE, DIPLOMACY AND GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP

This flagship aims to use the inspiring potential of astronomy to stimulate a sense of tolerance and common humanity. The beauty and scale of the universe can induce a 'universal' perspective which can influence how people interact with their fellow human beings and our planet. astro4dev.org/flagship-themes/celebrating-our-common-humanity-astronomy

PALE BLUE DOT

Pale Blue Dot is an education project that uses astronomy to promote a sense of global citizenship in young children. The cosmic perspective of our Earth is a powerful tool to stimulate solidarity, appreciation of other cultures and environmental awareness. Led by the IAU OAD European Regional Office, it builds on the Universe Awareness project and will develop hands-on educational materials for children that promote the message of global citizenship.

astro4dev.eu/projects/pale-blue-dot

"Before they are 10 years old, every child should be introduced to the inspiring notion that we all inhabit a tiny planet in a vast wonderful Universe, illustrated by the iconic pictures of our earth taken from space. This will help them realise that we all belong to a common humanity (SDG 4.7), who must respect and protect our planet (SDG 13) and advance the cause of peace (SDG 16)."

The session included a keynote from South African Minister of International Relations and Cooperation, Naledi Pandor, and MEP European Parliamentary Delegation for Relations with South Africa, Barry Andrews.

UNITED NATIONS GA75 DIALOGUE ON ASTRONOMY TO STIMULATE A GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE

In September 2020, the European Regional Office organised an online dialogue on "Astronomy – a Unique Educational Tool for furthering the SDGs and Stimulating a Global Perspective". It was part of the Intelligence in Science ScienceDigital online conference in the context of the United Nation's 75th anniversary.

The summary report and session recording are available on the website.

astro4dev.org/un-general-assembly-side-event-astronomy-a-unique-educational-tool-for-furthering-the-sdgs-stimulating-a-global-perspective

The dialogue considered whether introducing young children to the enormity and beauty of the Universe can stimulate a global perspective that will help advance (i) a peaceful world (SDG 16), (ii) the realisation that our planet must be protected from human pollution (SDG 13) and (iii) promote children's interest in science and technology (SDG 4). The session concluded that:

ASTRONOMY FOR MENTAL HEALTH

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, mental health disorders such as depression and anxiety contributed significantly to the global burden of disease. The increase in social isolation, economic inequity, political unrest, and other stressors have increased the prevalence of these illnesses across the world. Moreover, the measures taken to decrease the spread of the virus have drastically reduced the type and quantity of coping mechanisms available for people to take care of their mental health. In response to these problems, the project 'Astronomy for Mental Health' aims to explore how various modes of astronomy, including stargazing and education, can be a viable tool for improving mental well-being.

Findings in psychology research demonstrate that time spent in nature has positive effects on mental wellbeing, such as decreasing stress and increasing attention span. Additionally, research findings show that an experience which elicits a sense of awe increases altruistic behavior in humans. Astronomy lies at the intersection of these two phenomena—stargazing is a way for people to be exposed to natural environments, and perceiving and/or learning about the vastness of the universe is very often accompanied by an experience of awe. 'Astronomy for Mental Health' hopes to tap into these characteristics of astronomy in order to produce restorative effects and increase mental well-being.

astro4dev.org/astronomy-mental-health

ASTRONOMY KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS FOR DEVELOPMENT
 This flagship focuses on the use of knowledge and skills used in astronomy to tackle development challenges. This includes methods, techniques widely used in the field including data handling, data analysis, machine learning as well as the necessary compute facilities.

BIG DATA HACKATHONS

The OAD and DARA Big Data (Development in Africa through Radio Astronomy) in partnership with the Inter-University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy (IDiA) are organizing a number of Big Data Hackathons in Africa. The hackathons are part of a multi-year program, led by OAD-DARA Big Data Fellow Dr. Nikhita Madanpall, which aims to develop data science, programming and related skills in Africa in the context of huge radio astronomy projects. Nikhita has developed activities for the flagship including: guidelines for pilot projects, a COVID-19 hackathon project (analysis of COVID-related Twitter data); an image classification project; SETI hackathon project with Breakthrough Listen team..

third, organized at the Eduardo Mondlane University in Mozambique, involved the use of optical satellite imagery (from the Sentinel-2 satellite) to locate and monitor areas of flooding after a hurricane or cyclone. All hackathons were coordinated remotely by the OAD, DARA, and IDiA teams with the support of local tutors and collaborators on site. The hackthons are available on the Github repository.

astro4dev.org/big-data-hackathons

The first hackathon was held at the University of Zambia in September 2020. The theme of this hackathon was Natural Language Processing (NLP) and machine learning. Participants learned to collect and prepare COVID19-related Twitter data, then build a machine learning model to perform sentiment analysis on tweets from around the world. The second hackathon was organized in collaboration with DARA Big Data, the Space Generation Advisory Council, and IDiA. The

EVENTS

SAAO200 SYMPOSIUM**October 2020**

The South African Astronomical Observatory, host of the OAD in Cape Town, celebrated its 200th anniversary in 2020. The milestone was marked by a symposium, in addition to other activities. Drs Vanessa McBride and Amidou Sorgho from the OAD presented at SAAO200.

saa0200.saa0.ac.za

youtu.be/0RjUXyq6uxw

LORENTZ CENTER WORKSHOP: SPACE SCIENCE FOR SOCIETAL CHALLENGES**October 2020**

The European Union-funded projects spaceEU and Our Space Our Future hosted the online Lorentz Center 'Space Science for Societal Challenges' workshop to explore how different players in the European space sector can collaborate more effectively to address societal challenges. Drs Vanessa McBride and Tawanda Chingozha presented the OAD's work at the virtual event.

space-eu.org/space-workshop

youtu.be/uvP8W3Khkva

WORKSHOP

SAIP WEBINAR: IMPACT OF SCIENCE ON DEVELOPMENT- SHINING THE LIGHT ON ASTRONOMY**November 2020**

Drs Tawanda Chingozha and Amidou Sorgho presented a talk on the impact of science on development, based on their study at the astronomy observatory in Sutherland, South Africa.

facebook.com/watch/?v=422000288791650

DIALOGUE ON THE ROLE OF ASTRONOMY IN THE COVID-19 ERA**August 2020**

OAD Fellow Dr Marie Korsaga was a keynote speaker at the webinar on "A dialogue on the role of astronomy in the COVID-19 era" organized by the National Astronomical Research Institute of Thailand, host of the IAU OAD South East Asian Regional Office.

[facebook.com/watch/live/?ref=watch_permalink
&v=2429098824060123](https://facebook.com/watch/live/?ref=watch_permalink&v=2429098824060123)

DIALOGUE

VIRTUAL CONFERENCE

GLOBAL HANDS ON UNIVERSE VIRTUAL CONFERENCE

August 2020

OAD Director Kevin Govender gave a keynote talk at the GHOU 2020, a 5-day global meeting with talks, workshops, live astronomical observations, and more.

youtube.com/watch?v=4JndEj86rhg

WEBINAR

SAAO VIRTUAL COLLOQUIA

OAD team members Drs Marie Korsaga, Tawanda Chingozha, Amidou Sorgho, and Nikhita Madhanpall all gave talks at the SAAO virtual colloquia.

youtube.com/watch?v=JKsdl9CRsCs

youtube.com/watch?v=VPqTDbKyMxo

Webinar

“A Dialogue on the Role of Astronomy in the COVID-19 Era”

f LIVE

Host NARIT, IAU South East Asia regional office of OAD (SEAROAD)
 Date August 25, 2020
 Time 14:00 - 16:30 Thailand Time (07:00 - 09:30 UTC)

DISCUSSION

THE IMPACT OF RACIAL INEQUALITY IN DEVELOPMENT ECONOMICS

July 2020

Kevin Govender and Tawanda Chingozha discussed the impact of racial inequality in development economics in a virtual session of the Global Impact for Breakfast platform.

vimeo.com/440342975

The first major meeting of the **AFRICAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY** took place online in **March 2021**, with several OAD team members and regional offices presenting talks.

OAD Director Kevin Govender and Development Economist Tawanda Chingozha presented at the virtual **IAU-SHAW WORKSHOP** organized by the IAU Office of Astronomy for Education in **October 2020**.

OAD astronomer Vanessa McBride gave virtual talks at seminars organized by the **UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON, UNIVERSITY OF RADBOD AND UMASS LOWELL**.

Several OAD team members presented their work at the **FIFTH MIDDLE EAST AND AFRICA REGIONAL IAU MEETING (MEARIM V)** in **November 2020**. It was jointly hosted by the Regional Center for Space Science and Technology Education for Western Asia / United Nations, and Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Sciences (AUASS). MEARIM V was organized with the theme of "Astronomy education and research for the future generations".

Kevin Govender and Marie Korsaga, together with the European ROAD, participated in the **AERAP VIRTUAL CONFERENCE** in the session "Astronomy for Development, A unique African-European collaboration to advance the SDGs globally".

Kevin Govender, Ramasamy Venugopal and Amidou Sorgho attended the **EUROPEAN VENTURE PHILANTHROPY ASSOCIATION (EVPA) CONFERENCE** in **September**. This is an annual gathering of funders, where the OAD flagship relating to astrotourism was presented, together with Sonal Asgotraa and Paras Loomba, our partners from the Global Himalayan Expedition.

Vanessa McBride co-organised session SS15 Africa-European collaborations in astronomy and space science at the **EUROPEAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY ANNUAL MEETING** on **30 June 2020**. The OAD and its regional offices featured strongly in several other sessions with talks from the OAD (Vanessa McBride); the European Regional Office in Netherlands (Michelle Willebrands); the Andean Regional Office in Colombia (Jaime Forero-Romero); the Portuguese Language Office (Gustavo Rojas); the South East and Central Asian Regional Office in Armenia (Areg Mickaelian); the Southern African Regional Office in Zambia (Prosperity Simpemba); the West African Regional Office in Nigeria (Bonaventure Okere); and the East African Regional Office in Ethiopia (Alemiye Mamo).

Presentations were given on the IAU General Assembly 2024 at the "Astronomy and Space science: room to grow" session at the **EAS MEETING**; a special session at the **AFRICAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY** meeting; and a meeting of stakeholders within South Africa.

REGIONAL OFFICES

Regional Nodes and Language Expertise Centres (ROAD/LOAD) are offices based around the world with similar objectives as the OAD but with a regional focus. These offices work closely with the OAD in order to implement the IAU Strategic Plan. "Regions" which they focus on

could be geographical or cultural. As of 2021, there are 11 Regional Offices around the world. Below is a map of the offices and a selection of their activities in this period. Visit the OAD website for the entire list of activities.

**NORTH
AMERICA**

**ANDEAN
REGION**

EUROPE

**PORTUGUESE
LANGUAGE**

**WEST
AFRICA**

SOUTH WEST
AND CENTRAL ASIA

EAST ASIA
AND CHINESE
LANGUAGE

ARAB WORLD AND
ARABIC LANGUAGE

SOUTH EAST ASIA

EAST AFRICA

SOUTHERN
AFRICA

REGIONAL OFFICE/
LANGUAGE CENTRE

NORTH AMERICA

- ◆ The NA-ROAD is working on the development of a 5-year Strategic Plan and will organize an advisory board that will work closely with the NA-ROAD Governing Council.
- ◆ The office conducted a Needs Assessment of North America to help identify future partners and collaborators, and provide critical information for use in its strategic planning efforts.

ANDEAN

- ◆ The Andean-ROAD is working on the development of a 5-year Strategic Plan and will organize an advisory board with leadership rotating among the countries.
- ◆ The office approached Argentinean astronomers, Office of Astronomy for Education in Colombia and universities from Colombia and Ecuador to collaborate in the Second Workshop on Astronomy Beyond the Common Senses for Accessibility and Inclusion.
- ◆ The office invited teachers from all over the Andean region to share their experiences and methodologies to teach astronomy at school at the 1st Regional Meeting of Classroom Under the Sky.

EUROPE

- ◆ The office organized 3 sessions at the EAS2020 Annual Conference – "Astronomy for Future: Development, global citizenship & climate action", "Astronomy for Development", "Astronomy for Future: Maintaining world-class research and collaboration in the climate crisis".
- ◆ An Erasmus+ proposal led by the European Office together with the Andean, West African, East African, and South West & Central Asian Regional Offices was successful.
- ◆ Together with spaceEU, the office organized a Dialogue on 'Astronomy- a Unique Educational Tool for furthering the

SDGs and Stimulating a Global Perspective' as part of the ISC Intelligence in Science ScienceDigital @ UNGA75 online conference.

- ◆ The office consolidated the discussions of the spaceEU Lorentz workshop in a white paper, which was widely disseminated across astronomy and space networks, as well as EU policy-makers.
- ◆ The H2020 EU SKIES project was officially launched on March 1, 2021 with an online kick-off meeting with representatives from all the consortium partners.

PORTUGUESE LANGUAGE

- ◆ The office took part in a joint broadcast with members from Brazil, Cape Verde, Mozambique and Portugal to celebrate the Portuguese Language Day (May 5).
- ◆ A webinar hosted on International Women's Day: "The experience of being a woman and a scientist in Portuguese-speaking countries" was organized in partnership with Revista Galileu (the largest popular science magazine in Portuguese)
- ◆ Promotion of "Cartas Com Ciência" initiative (mail exchange between children and scientists) in Portuguese speaking countries.
- ◆ PLOAD participated in the inaugural event of the OruMbya project, supported by the IAU OAD .

WEST AFRICA

- ◆ The office, in collaboration with the European ROAD secured an Erasmus+ mobility grant to fund staff and student exchange in Astronomy.
- ◆ The office established an astronomy club in Cameroon and also participated in the June 21st 2020 Solar Eclipse and the July 4 Lunar Eclipse.

- ◆ The Pan-Africa Planetary and Space Science Network mobility grant secured by the office in collaboration with other 9 institutions is ongoing. The project is on human capacity development.
- ◆ The office organized the "Vanishing and Appearing Sources over a Century of Observation" citizen science project. Participants were drawn from Nigeria and Cameroon. The program is on the Search for Extra Terrestrial Intelligence (SETI) and involves the analysis of sky survey images.

EAST AFRICA

- ◆ The Ethiopian Space Science and Technology Institute (ESSTI) and the International Astronomical Union renewed their agreement to continue hosting the East African Regional Office in Addis Ababa for the next 5 years.
astro4dev.org/ethiopia-renews-agreement-iau-regional-office
- ◆ The office played a major role in organizing events celebrating the June 2020 annual solar eclipse in East Africa and Ethiopia.

SOUTHERN AFRICA

- ◆ The office organized an online training for science teachers in Zambia on Inquiry Learning Spaces, with facilitators from Nigeria and Kenya under GOGA project in Africa.
- ◆ The office is developing an MSc program in astrophysics which can be adapted by institutions of higher learning in the region.
- ◆ An MOU for renewal of hosting the office was signed between the IAU and the Copperbelt University for another term of three years.
- ◆ The year ended sadly with the passing of a member of the Steering Committee, Dr. Habatwa Mweene, and the Country Coordinator for Zambia, Mr. Nchimunya Mwiinga.
- ◆

ARAB

- ◆ The office organized several public lectures, seminars, and courses via Zoom together with the Jordanian Astronomical Society (JAS), the Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Science (AUASS) and other Jordanian & Arab institutions.

SOUTH WEST AND CENTRAL ASIA

- ◆ The Byurakan Astrophysical Observatory and the IAU renewed their agreement to host the South West and Central Asian Regional Office for another 6 years (2022–2027).
astro4dev.org/armenia-will-continue-to-host-the-iau-regional-office
- ◆ The 7th Byurakan International Summer School for Young Astronomers was organized on the topic of "Astronomy and Data Science".
- ◆ An astro tourism website with information from regional countries was prepared for the IAU100 Astro-tourism project
iau-swa-road.aras.am/eng/AstroTourism

EAST ASIA AND CHINESE LOAD

- ◆ Public outreach events were organized including visits to high schools and a series of lectures.

SOUTH EAST ASIA

- ◆ SEA-ROAD Webinar "A Dialogue on the Role of Astronomy in the COVID-19 Era" highlighted the significance of astronomy as a tool to tackle COVID-19 pandemic.
- ◆ The office provided astronomy booklets for Laos and supported the print out of 8,000 copies.

06

PARTNER SHIPS ✨

INTER-UNIVERSITY CENTRE FOR ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS (IUCAA), INDIA

Inter-University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics (IUCAA), India is one of the leading research institutes in astronomy/astrophysics globally. IUCAA also has a well renowned program of public outreach and education (SciPop). Since our establishment, OAD and IUCAA have enjoyed close ties. This partnership paves way for specific collaborations in capacity development along education, development and outreach.

ROYAL ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (RAS), UK

Royal Astronomical Society (RAS), UK encourages and promotes the study of astronomy, solar-system science, geophysics and closely related branches of science. The RAS and OAD have partnered to establish or nurture research, educational and/or development related collaborations between the UK and countries where astronomy research is not well established.

SPACE GENERATION ADVISORY COUNCIL (SGAC)

Space Generation Advisory Council (SGAC) in support of the United Nations Programme on Space Applications is a global non-governmental, non-profit (US 501(c)3) organisation and network which aims to represent

university students and young space professionals ages 18-35 to the United Nations, space agencies, industry, and academia. Both OAD and SGAC have common goals in strengthening global networks in space and astronomy and developing capacity in STEM fields.

DEVELOPMENT OF AFRICA THROUGH RADIO ASTRONOMY (DARA)

Development of Africa through Radio Astronomy (DARA) is a joint UK – South Africa Newton funded project that uses radio astronomy training to develop high level technical skills in young graduates. The partnership is an implementation of the astronomy-for-development concept and involves collaboration at both strategy and project evaluation levels.

INTERNATIONAL VIRTUAL OBSERVATORY ALLIANCE (IVOA)

The IVOA was formed in June 2002 and aims to facilitate international coordination and collaboration in tools, systems and organizational structures for astronomical archives. The IVOA now comprises 20 Virtual Observatory programmes from Argentina, Armenia, Australia, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Europe, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Italy, Japan, Russia, South Africa, Spain,

Ukraine, the United Kingdom, and the United States and an inter-governmental organization (ESA). The purpose of the partnership is to bring together the complementary resources and expertise of the IVOA and the OAD to advance the application of astronomical data and/or technology use in different areas of society, most notably for education, development and public outreach.

Council, and aims to develop big data skills using radio astronomy in SKA African partner countries. Through a partnership with DARA Big Data, the OAD hosts a fellow, Dr Nikhita Madhanpall, who is working on hackathons that expose students and young people to big data and machine learning in both astronomy and development-related contexts.

DARA BIG DATA

The Development in Africa with Radio Astronomy (DARA) Big Data Project is funded by the United Kingdom Newton Fund via the Science and Technologies Facilities

The OAD is always open to partnerships with other organisations wishing to be proactive in the area of science for development. If your organisation wishes to partner with the OAD, contact us at info@astro4dev.org.

FINANCIAL ✨ INFORMATION ✨

COMPLIANCE

The OAD operates within the financial systems and policies of the National Research Foundation (NRF), which comply with South African legislation. Compliance of the OAD's financial transactions to the relevant policies is tested through annual audits of the South African Astronomical Observatory (SAAO) and NRF. The OAD financial year (April to March) is different as compared to the implementation of funded projects (calendar year), and long-term special projects or grants (which can be multi-year).

OPERATIONS

For the duration of the IAU-NRF agreement, the OAD receives an annual core income from the DSI/NRF and the IAU, all administered through the NRF. Since the renewed IAU-NRF agreement in 2015, the DSI/NRF provides R1,500,000 per year with an annual inflationary increase of 6%, plus the salary and associated costs of a full-time OAD astronomer. The IAU provides a fixed amount of €70,000 per year, plus the salary and associated costs of a part-time fundraiser. In addition, the IAU funds the annual call for proposals (€120,000 per year). Since 2016, these project grants have been paid directly from the IAU in Paris. The total allocation for 2021 projects was €109,944, with the remainder reserved for contingencies such as top-ups required due to unforeseen COVID-related circumstances.

INCOME

For the 2020–2021 financial year, the DSI/NRF provided R3,300,000 and the IAU provided R1,293,380 (total core income of R4,593,380). In addition, the OAD received project income from DARA Big Data, African Astronomical Society and African Planetarium Association totalling R640,183. There was also a carryover of R1,006,586 due mainly to unfilled positions over the past few years. At the end of the year, there was still a surplus of R730,847, which will be fully utilised in the next financial year on the multi-year flagship projects.

EXPENDITURE

The 2020–2021 financial year has been exceptional in that the effects of the pandemic started being felt in March 2020, just before the start of the year, when all travel and meetings were cancelled, and have still not resumed to pre-pandemic levels. This meant that much of the budgeted travel and conference costs were unspent. The OAD took the decision early on to redirect these funds into an extraordinary call for COVID-related projects, which was launched in May 2020, as well as the three flagship projects. The largest expenses for the financial year were therefore salaries (R2,924,515) and project funding (R2,355,457), which far outweigh other operational costs that were virtually negligible due to the work-from-home and travel restrictions for the duration of the entire financial year.

INCOME

- ◆ IAU (€70,000 p.a.)
- ◆ DSI (R1.5m + 6% p.a. plus R1m staffing)
- ◆ OTHER INCOME (projects and postdoc grants)
- ◆ CARRYOVER OF OPERATING EXPENSES
- ◆ IAU PROJECT FUNDING (€120,000)

EXPENSES

- ◆ STAFF EXPENSES (salaries, fellows, consultants, recruitment, training)
- ◆ OFFICE EXPENSES (infrastructure and running costs)
- ◆ SUBSISTENCE AND TRAVEL
- ◆ WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCES
- ◆ PRODUCTION, PRINTING AND DISTRIBUTION OF MATERIALS
- ◆ OAD SPECIAL PROJECTS (COVID call and Flagships)
- ◆ IAU PROJECT GRANTS AND CONTINGENCIES (€109,944+€10,056)

